

METHODS FOR INTELLIGENT ANALYSIS OF SOIL COMPOSITION USING MODERN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE MODELS

Nazarov Fayzullo^{1, a}, Akhatov Abror^{1, b}

¹Samarkand State University named after Sharof Rashidov Samarkand, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17919307>

Abstract. *Methods for intelligent analysis of soil composition data based on modern artificial intelligence algorithms are important in increasing agricultural efficiency and ensuring a sustainable ecology. The study examined methods for analyzing soil data using machine learning algorithms to overcome some of the shortcomings of traditional laboratory methods for this process. The most modern methods were considered, from processing datasets to training them in artificial intelligence models. These methods can be used to perform real-time analysis processes in agriculture.*

Keywords: *Soil composition, intellectual analysis, chemical property, ensemble learning, confusion matrix, crop type, imputation, classification*

Introduction. Soil is the most important resource in agriculture, and its composition and quality determine not only agricultural efficiency but also global ecological sustainability. Today, due to environmental changes, rapid population growth, and resource limitations, accurate assessment of soil conditions is a pressing issue [1]. Although traditional laboratory analyses and other methods provide high accuracy in this regard, their main disadvantages are their time-consuming nature, high cost, and dependence on the human factor. As a result, agricultural operators face difficulties and delays in decision-making [2].

Every day, new possibilities to address this issue are presented by machine learning and artificial intelligence technology. When compared to laboratory examination, machine learning models can save 77% of time by simultaneously analyzing multidimensional features of soil composition with an accuracy of up to 95% [3]. In developing countries, soil data is acquired using a range of sensors and equipment. Data obtained via these devices is frequently incomplete and noisy for a variety of reasons. In this scenario, machine learning algorithms ensure that intellectual analysis is carried out correctly by processing and filling in data while also decreasing noise [4].

The main aim of this study is to create new techniques for intelligent soil composition analysis utilizing cutting-edge artificial intelligence algorithms and assess their applicability. The study focused at how to properly prepare a dataset for intelligent analysis, analyze soil features using artificial intelligence algorithms, and predict crop type based on soil data [5].

Materials and methods. This research covers the steps from preprocessing the dataset to training and evaluating the models for the intelligent soil composition analysis process. The work done is mainly based on artificial intelligence algorithms, which are aimed at overcoming the difficulties of working with data in the process of intellectual analysis [6]. Several modern methods of preprocessing the dataset were considered and the most suitable methods were selected.

Dataset. The study’s dataset, which combined data on crop-specific traits and soil composition, was gathered from a number of free sources. The collection, which has 5816 rows, includes information on soil composition that is thought to be fertile for crops like corn, wheat, cotton, and carrots. Table 1 below provides general information regarding the dataset [7-8].

Table 1. General information about the dataset

Feature property	Features	Units	Data type
Identification property	Sample	-	Categorical
Physical property	Layer	cm	Categorical
	Mechanical composition	-	Categorical
	CF	%	Numerical
	Soil density	g/cm ³	Numerical
Chemical property	pH	-	Numerical
	Soil EC	mS/cm	Numerical
	N	mg/kg	Numerical
	P	mg/kg	Numerical
	K	mg/kg	Numerical
	Mg	mg/kg	Numerical
	S	mg/kg	Numerical
	Zn	mg/kg	Numerical
	Mn	mg/kg	Numerical
	B	mg/kg	Numerical
	Fe	mg/kg	Numerical
Cu	mg/kg	Numerical	
Organic property	Humus	%	Numerical
Biological property	Microorganisms	CFU/g	Numerical
Target variable	Crop	-	Categorical

The identification feature group in Table 1 above is used for sample identification, and the physical and chemical properties of the soil are used to determine its fertility levels. The organic property determines the amount of humus in the soil, while the biological property determines the number of active microorganisms in it [9,10,11]. It is necessary to select the crop type as the target variable.

NaN (Not a number) values in the dataset. The NaN values in this dataset are mainly due to the merging of multiple datasets, as noted above. Fig. 2 below shows the amount of NaN values in the dataset.

Fig. 2. NaN values in a dataset (across all columns)

As can be seen in Fig. 2 above, the NaN values in the dataset are mainly related to the columns Microorganisms (CFU/g), B (mg/kg), and Mn (mg/kg). Usually, such columns are discarded when processing a dataset, but in an agricultural dataset, these properties are considered very important for soil composition. Therefore, deleting these columns may negatively affect the model results. In this case, the most appropriate solution is to fill in NaN values [12].

Preprocessing the dataset. Preprocessing a dataset entails carrying out a number of tasks, including converting, normalizing, and filling in NaN values. Since many imputation techniques only work with numeric values, it is required to transform categorical data to numeric type before filling in NaN values [13]. Converting categorical values to numerical values can be done in a number of ways. One technique for transforming categorical variables to ordered integers is called ordinal encoding [14].

Imputation methods are usually used to solve the problem of filling in NaN values in a data set. In this study, we used the Fast MICE method to solve this problem. The Fast MICE method is an accelerated version of Multiple Imputation by Chained Equations (MICE). The Fast MICE method works through an iterative regression chain based on the MICE method but significantly speeds up the calculation by using fewer iterations and higher tolerance [15]. The working process of this method is that in the initial stage, missing values for each numeric column are filled with the mean, median, or most frequently occurring values. In each iteration, missing values were predicted in the study using Ridge regression. In the next step, missing values were updated and the algorithm stopped after the number of iterations was completed [15-16]. In this study, NaN values in the dataset were filled in using the Fast MICE imputation method with mean values.

Fig. 3. Comparison of original and imputed soil data.

In Fig. 3 above, the actual values of the soil properties in the dataset are shown in blue, and the values filled in by Fast MICE are shown in red. Once the dataset is processed, it can be tested on artificial intelligence algorithms.

Dataset training and evaluation. The study used modern ensemble machine learning classification algorithms, such as Random Forest and Gradient Boosting, to predict crops by analyzing soil composition. These algorithms are characterized by high accuracy and stability in unbalanced datasets and allow for the assessment of the importance of features [17].

Random Forest is an ensemble method consisting of multiple decision trees, each tree trained on a random subset of the data and a random subset of the features. The final prediction is made by majority voting. The Gradient Boosting algorithm is a boosting method that builds a strong model by successively adding weak learners. The main goal of this algorithm is that each

new tree aims to correct the errors of previous models [18]. The research results were obtained by training the dataset to these ensemble algorithms and evaluating the accuracy of the algorithms.

Results and Discussion. As mentioned above, ensemble algorithms of artificial intelligence were used in the process of classifying crop types by analyzing soil data in the dataset. As a result, Random Forest and Gradient Boosting classification models were applied to the test dataset and the following results were achieved. The overall accuracy of the Random Forest model was 0.8832. The Gradient Boosting model produced a result with an accuracy of 0.9003. These results are considered high indicators for an unbalanced dataset. The following are the indicators of the model in terms of confusion matrix, accuracy metrics, and detailed evaluation metrics by class.

Fig. 4. Confusion matrix of the Random Forest and Gradient Boosting classification algorithms

Fig. 4 above shows the confusion matrix showing the results of the two algorithms. These images help to visually represent the relationship between the model's actual classes and predicted classes. From the results in these images, it can be seen that the predictions of the Gradient Boosting classifier are slightly higher between the two algorithms.

Table 2. Accuracy results of ensemble machine learning algorithms on various metrics

Model	Parameters	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Random Forest	n_est = 100 random_state=42	0.8832	0.8829	0.8832	0.8828
Gradient Boosting	n_est = 100 lear_rate = 0.1	0.9003	0.8997	0.9003	0.8997

As can be seen from Table 2 above, ensemble machine learning algorithms performed well in predicting crop classification using soil composition data.

Conclusion. This study was aimed at developing methods for intelligent analysis of soil composition based on modern artificial intelligence algorithms and evaluating their practical effectiveness. The results of the study show that ensemble machine learning algorithms provide high accuracy to overcome the limitations of traditional laboratory methods. Modern methods

also help to preserve the internal relationships of data when processing datasets and increase the stability of the model. The practical significance of the study is that the proposed methods can automate real-time soil analysis in agricultural practice, obtain crop recommendations based on soil sensor data, save significant resources and significantly increase productivity. At the same time, the dataset tested in the study may have some limitations, as it was collected from various sources and classified only four crop classes. In the future, such methods can be expanded by integrating deep learning models based on multimodal data. Overall, the role of artificial intelligence in soil analysis as a technological innovation can positively contribute to transforming agriculture.

REFERENCES

1. Folorunso, O., Ojo, O., Busari, M., Adebayo, M., Joshua, A., Folorunso, D., Ugwunna, C. O., Olabanjo, O., & Olabanjo, O. (2023). Exploring Machine Learning Models for Soil Nutrient Properties Prediction: A Systematic Review. *Big Data and Cognitive Computing*, 7(2), 113. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bdcc7020113>
2. Awais, M., Naqvi, S.M.Z.A., Zhang, H. et al. AI and machine learning for soil analysis: an assessment of sustainable agricultural practices. *Bioresour. Bioprocess.* 10, 90 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40643-023-00710-y>
3. Afzal, H., Amjad, M., Raza, A. et al. Incorporating soil information with machine learning for crop recommendation to improve agricultural output. *Sci Rep* 15, 8560 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-88676-z>
4. F.Nazarov., A.Akhatov. METHODS FOR PREPARING A DATA SET FOR DETERMINING SOIL FERTILITY BASED ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE MODELS . (2025). DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE, 3(2), 91-99. <https://dtai.tsue.uz/index.php/dtai/article/view/v3i215>
5. Mundada, S., Jain, P. Predicting soil organic carbon with ensemble learning techniques by using satellite images for precision farming. *Sci Rep* 15, 28760 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-09804-3>
6. Sobhy, D. M., & Anandhi, A. (2025). Soil Nutrient Monitoring Technologies for Sustainable Agriculture: A Systematic Review. *Sustainability*, 17(18), 8477. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17188477>
7. A. Kayum and M. O. Rahman, "Appropriate Crop Recommended System for Cultivation using IoT and ML," 2023 5th International Conference on Sustainable Technologies for Industry 5.0 (STI), Dhaka, Bangladesh, 2023, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/STI59863.2023.10464865.
8. B. Qian, T. Huffman and R. De Jong, "Simulated crop productivity on different soils in Canada," 2012 IEEE 4th International Symposium on Plant Growth Modeling, Simulation, Visualization and Applications, Shanghai, China, 2012, pp. 312-315, doi: 10.1109/PMA.2012.6524851.
9. Bekier, J., Jamroz, E., Walenczak-Bekier, K., & Uściła, M. (2023). Soil Organic Matter Composition in Urban Soils: A Study of Wrocław Agglomeration, SW Poland. *Sustainability*, 15(3), 2277. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15032277>
10. W. R. Scott and G. S. Smith, "Measured electrical constitutive parameters of soil as functions of frequency and moisture content," in *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 621-623, May 1992, doi: 10.1109/36.142943.

11. Ardiansyah, D.; Huda, A.S.M.; Tosida, E.T.; Bon, A.T. Wireless sensor networks for soil nutrition to increase agricultural productivity. In Proceedings of the 5th NA International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management, Detroit, MI, USA, 10–14 August 2020.
12. A. Akhatov, N. Fayzulla and M. Eshmurodov, "Ensemble Machine Learning Algorithms for Crop Types Classification Based on Intelligent Detection of Soil Properties," 2025 International Russian Automation Conference (RusAutoCon), Sochi, Russian Federation, 2025, pp. 691-696, doi: 10.1109/RusAutoCon65989.2025.11177338.
13. A. Sadhu, R. Soni and M. Mishra, "Pattern-based Comparative Analysis of Techniques for Missing Value Imputation," 2020 IEEE 5th International Conference on Computing Communication and Automation (ICCCA), Greater Noida, India, 2020, pp. 513-518, doi: 10.1109/ICCCA49541.2020.9250825.
14. Bolikulov, F., Nasimov, R., Rashidov, A., Akhmedov, F., & Cho, Y.-I. (2024). Effective Methods of Categorical Data Encoding for Artificial Intelligence Algorithms. *Mathematics*, 12(16), 2553. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math12162553>
15. Buuren, Stef & Groothuis-Oudshoorn, Catharina. (2011). MICE: Multivariate Imputation by Chained Equations in R. *Journal of Statistical Software*. 45. 10.18637/jss.v045.i03.
16. Aracri, F., Bianco, M. G., Quattrone, A., & Sarica, A. (2025). Bridging the Gap: Missing Data Imputation Methods and Their Effect on Dementia Classification Performance. *Brain Sciences*, 15(6), 639. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci15060639>
17. Breiman, L. Random Forests. *Machine Learning* 45, 5–32 (2001). <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1010933404324>
18. Hossen, M.K., Uddin, M.S. From data to insights: Using gradient boosting classifier to optimize student engagement in online classes with explainable AI. *Educ Inf Technol* 30, 18089–18130 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-025-13500-0>